

The Effect of Unemployment, Economic Growth and Poverty Levels on the Rate of Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency in 2012-2021

Hanifa Sri Nuryani¹⁾

Management Economics Study Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, Sumbawa University Of Technology, Indonesia.

Edi Irawan²⁾

Development Economics Study Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, Sumbawa University Of Technology, Indonesia.

Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the influence of unemployment, economic growth and poverty levels on the rate of human development index in Sumbawa district in 2012-2021. The research method used in this study is a quantitative method. Analysis of the data used is the multiple linear regression method. The results of the study show that the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, the economic growth rate of Sumbawa Regency and the poverty rate of Sumbawa Regency simultaneously have a significant effect on the rate of the human development index level in Sumbawa Regency in 2012 - 2021. This can be seen in the F Test where the significance value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Then the second independent variable is the unemployment rate ($0.004 < 0.005$). The independent variable, the level of economic growth, does not have a significant effect, this is because the economy in Sumbawa Regency is still dominated by the agricultural sector. Then there are still development imbalances between several regions in the West Nusa Tenggara Province, so that it affects the human development index in Sumbawa Regency.

Keywords:- Human Development Index, Sumbawa Regency.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Human Development Index is used to see the extent to which the success of development and human welfare of a region or country, the reasons why human development needs attention are: first, many developing countries including Indonesia have succeeded in achieving economic growth, but failed to reduce socio-economic inequality and poverty. Second, many developed countries that have high income levels have not succeeded in reducing social problems, such as: drug abuse, AIDS, alcohol, homelessness, and domestic violence. Third, some low-income countries are able to achieve high levels of human development because they are able to wisely use all resources to develop basic human abilities. In theory, if economic growth increases, the Human Development Index will increase because if economic growth in an area is high, then capital expenditures will also increase so that it will have an impact on increasing the Human Development Index [23]. Then if the poverty line is increasing and people are not able to meet their basic needs, then low income will then result in low demand so that investment is also low and can reduce productivity.

In a study conducted by Kahang et al., [10], that the development of the development paradigm for a country is not only measured by the level of economic growth, but also by paying attention to the level of human development including the quality of human life in an area or country. In addition, development theory tends to place a lot of emphasis on the accumulation aspect of human capital where this is done through the creation of a more productive generation through improving the quality of knowledge, improving nutrition and health as well as improving the quality of skills. The development of a country can be assessed using the Human Development Index. Standards of living, health and proper education are measures in calculating the Human Development Index level [1]. A country can be categorized as a developed country, developing or considered a lagging country by looking at how high the Human Development Index value is in that country.

The welfare of the community cannot be separated from how much income they get. Wages for the community is a source of income. If there is an increase in the amount of income, of course it will have an impact on their welfare. On the other hand, if wages decrease, it will have an impact on increasing poverty levels [16]. The policy regarding district and city minimum wages is expected to be able to improve the welfare of the community. In addition to providing a guarantee of income for the work of workers, the minimum wage policy is also expected to be a medium for the distribution of equitable development in each region. Increasing people's income in each region will also be able to reduce inequality between regions and have an impact on reducing the rate of migration of rural residents to cities [11]. The policy regarding the minimum wage will also ultimately provide added value for increasing people's purchasing power.

Income inequality in the community has an impact on the formation of a poverty gap [18]. Poverty itself is a problem in every country, and is often a problem that has almost no end. Poverty will result in a decrease in people's living standards so that it has an impact on the limited fulfillment of daily needs [15]. The powerlessness of the community in meeting basic needs is a general understanding of poverty (Sartika et al., 2016). On the other hand, poverty is the root of other social problems, both the problem of crime and the inability of the poor to get access to education and health and proper employment. This of course will have an impact on the welfare of the community itself.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The inability to access education and health as well as proper employment in turn has an impact on the increase in the number of unemployed in the workforce. In other words, poverty can have an impact on unemployment and lack of income, and then unemployment itself causes the formation of a poor community. If the cycle of unemployment and poverty is not cut with easy access to education and health as well as creating jobs, it will continue to be a never ending cycle. Government policies in the field of education in an effort to eradicate poverty will not have a significant impact if they are not balanced with policies in the field of employment [19].

Sumbawa Regency is one of the regencies in West Nusa Tenggara Province with a population in 2021 of 509,753 people. Data from the Central Statistics Agency for Sumbawa Regency shows the Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency as much as 63.12 percent. On the other hand, the rate of the poor population is 63.13 percent. Then the economic growth rate of Sumbawa Regency is 6.77 percent. Where the previous data, in 2020, showed that the Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency was 63.72. Then the poverty rate is 63.49 and the economic growth rate of Sumbawa Regency is 6.71. (Central Bureau of Statistics of Sumbawa Regency, 2021). Based on these data, there is a significant increase caused by one of the supporting factors, namely the rate of economic growth in Sumbawa Regency.

Many studies related to the Human Development Index have been carried out, but have shown inconsistent results. Research conducted [9] found that the degree of poverty did not have a significant effect on the level of the human development index. The results were different from the research findings of Muliza et al. [14] and Umiyati et al. [26] which shows that poverty has a significant and negative effect on the human development index. Meanwhile, in a different case, the results of Meydiasari & Soejoto's research [12] show that unemployment has a negative and significant impact on increasing the human development index. Likewise, similar empirical results were obtained by a number of experts (Meydiasari & Soejoto, [12]; Baeti, [5]; Hamzah et al., [7]; Ningrum et al., [16]; Arizal & Marwan, [3]; Syofya, [12]) who identified that unemployment has a negative impact on the human development index.

So this study aims to focus on the combination of previous research with current research, only the place and time have different values from previous research. With the hope that the results of research with the same variables as previous studies but at different times and places can give different results in terms of research analysis. The topic of this research will raise about analyzing the effect of unemployment, economic growth and poverty rate on the rate of human development index in Sumbawa district in 2012-2021.

A. Human Development Index

UNDP first used the human development index indicator in 1990 [9]. Human Development Index is defined by UNDP as a process in expanding the range of choices for the population with regard to income, health, education, environment and so on. Each region should make the full scope of human development the focus of the development process. It aims to improve the quality of life of the community physically, mentally and spiritually.

The benefits that can be obtained by calculating the human development index include the role of the human development index as a parameter of the level of success in building the quality of life in the community. Appropriate and good human development can increase the level of community welfare [8]. In addition, the human development index can be used in determining the ranking of one region/country with another. On the other hand, the human development index is also a parameter of a government's performance due to the government's role as a facilitator and catalyst factor in the development process. The high value of the human development index, in other words, is a reflection of the increasing level of population welfare [2].

The average development achievement of a country or region in using the human development index is measured based on three parameters, namely education, health and economy. Health level is measured by taking into account life expectancy at birth; education level is measured by looking at the average length of schooling; and, economic degree (decent living) is seen using purchasing power or gross national income per capita.

B. Poverty

Nowadays the definition of poverty is becoming more complex, where the dimensions of poverty include the problem of vulnerability, powerlessness and the inability to convey information. This makes poverty more multidimensional in society. Poverty is also considered as inequality of opportunity in accumulating social power in the form of capital and assets, social networks in obtaining jobs, goods and services. The inability to obtain knowledge and skills as well as useful information in the progress of their lives can also be assessed as poverty [20].

C. Unemployment

Unemployment is defined as the condition of a person who is already included in the labor force and who is actively looking for work for a certain level of wages, but that person does not get the job he wants. Furthermore, open unemployment is part of the labor force who have not worked and are looking for work [23].

D. Economic Growth

According to Todaro [25] there are three main factors or components in the economic growth of each country, namely: 1) Capital accumulation, which includes all forms or types of new investments invested in land, physical equipment, and capital or human resources; 2) Population growth, which in the

next few years will increase the number of workers; and 3) Technological progress, which is considered the most important source of economic growth and can be classified into three, namely: (a) neutral technological progress; (b) technological advances that save labour; (c) capital-saving technological advances.

In line with Todaro, Simon Kuznets in Arsyad [4] defines a country's economic growth as an increase in a country's ability to provide economic goods for its population, the increase in this ability is caused by technological advances, institutions, and the necessary ideological adjustments. Economic development is efforts to improve the standard of living of a nation which is usually measured by the level of real income per capita, the purpose of economic development is to increase real national income as well as to increase productivity. According to Todaro [25], development must be viewed as a multidimensional process that includes various fundamental changes to social structures, attitudes of society, and national institutions, in addition to continuing to pursue accelerated economic growth, handling income inequality, and alleviating poverty. Economic growth is a process where there is an increase in real gross national product or real national income, the economy is said to be growing or developing if there is real output growth, while economic development shows the output structure and input allocation in various economic sectors.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative and the data in this study are secondary data. According to the collection of data in this study is periodic data (time series). The time series data used is annual data for 10 (ten) years, namely 2012-2021. The data is taken from the Central Bureau of Statistics of Sumbawa Regency which is related to the number of research variables which include data on the level of the human development index level of Sumbawa Regency as the dependent variable (Y) and the independent variable, namely the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency (X1), the rate of growth, the rate of growth Sumbawa Regency's economy (X2) and Sumbawa Regency's Poverty Rate (X3). The data processing uses Statistical Product and Service Solution 20 (SPSS 20) software. The data analysis method used is the multiple regression method with the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique. To determine the effect of the independent variables, namely the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency (X1), Sumbawa Regency's economic growth rate (X2) and Sumbawa Regency's poverty rate (X3) which affect the Sumbawa Regency's Human Development Index level for 10 years, the regression equation is used. as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \mu_i \dots\dots$$

Description:

Y = Rate of Human Development Index Rate of Sumbawa Regency.

X1 = Unemployment rate in Sumbawa district.

X2 = Economic growth rate of Sumbawa Regency.

X3 = Poverty rate of Sumbawa Regency.

Bo = Constant coefficient

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_2$ & β_3 = Regression coefficient

μ_i = Error Term.

In using regression analysis tools, it is necessary to test the classical assumptions, so that the results of this regression analysis show a valid relationship. Among them are: (1) normality test, (2) multicollinearity test, (3) autocorrelation test and (4) heteroscedasticity test. Then after the model is free from classical assumption testing, it is continued with statistical justification. Statistical justification is a test of giving goodness of fit model that concerns the accuracy of the sample regression function in estimating the actual value by looking at its Goodness of Fit. Statistically, at least this can be measured from the value of the coefficient of determination, the value of the F statistic and the value of the t statistic [6].

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Findings

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the SPSS 2.0 program, the value of the Coefficient of Determination (R2) is obtained as follows:

The value of the coefficient of determination (R2) is as follows

Table 1. Determination Test Results

Model Summary			
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.997 ^a	.994	.991	30.093
a. Predictors: (Constant), Economic Growth, Poverty Rate, Unemployment			
Source: Processed Data 2022			

Based on Table 1. it can be seen that the coefficient of determination obtained is 0.994. This means that X1 (Unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency), X2 (Sumbawa Regency's economic growth rate) and X3 (Sumbawa Regency's poverty rate) affect the Sumbawa Regency's human development index rate (Y) of 99.4% while the rest 0.6% is influenced by other causal factors not examined in this study. In other words, the magnitude of the influence of the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, Sumbawa Regency's economic growth rate and Sumbawa Regency's Poverty Level on the Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency is 99.4% while the remaining 0.6% is influenced by other factors outside this regression model.

To determine the effect simultaneously or jointly on the three independent variables (the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, the economic growth rate in Sumbawa Regency and the poverty rate in Sumbawa Regency) on the analysis that affects the human development index in Sumbawa Regency for the 2012-2021 period, it is used The F test aims to determine whether the independent variables included in the regression model have a simultaneous (simultaneous) effect on the dependent variable. This test uses the F test, with an analysis based on a comparison between the significance value and the significance level (α) used or (α) 5%. If the significance of $F < 0.05$ then H_a is accepted, meaning that the independent variable simultaneously has a

significant effect on the dependent variable. The results of the F test analysis can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. F-Test Results on Variables of Economic Growth Rate, Poverty Rate and Unemployment Rate That Affect Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency 2012-2021.

ANOVA ^a					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	872080.740	3	290693.580	320.992	.000 ^b
Residual	5433.660	6	905.610		
Total	877514.400	9			
a. Dependent Variable: Human Development Index					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Economic Growth, Poverty Rate, Unemployment					

Source: Processed Data 2022

Based on Table 2 above, the significance value obtained from the F test table above is smaller than the significance value = 0.05 or 0.000 < 0.05 so that Ha is declared accepted. So it can be concluded that Ha is accepted, which means that the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, the economic growth rate in Sumbawa Regency and the poverty rate in Sumbawa Regency simultaneously have a significant effect on the rate of the human development index level in Sumbawa Regency.

B. Discussion

Based on the results of data processing related to the effect of unemployment, economic growth and poverty rates on the rate of human development index in Sumbawa Regency in 2012-2021. Following the results of data processing using SPSS 2.0 software, the regression results are shown in table 3.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Results on Variables of Economic Growth Rate, Poverty Rate and Unemployment Rate That Affect Human Development Index in Sumbawa Regency 2012-2021.

Coefficients ^a					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	15476.279	1172.749		13.197	.000
Unemployment	3.213	.699	.565	4.594	.004
Poverty Rate	-1.543	.101	-1.326	15.334	.000
Economic Growth	-.531	1.179	-.039	-.450	.668
a. Dependent Variable: Human Development Index					

Source: Processed Data 2022

Based on Table 3. the results of multiple linear regression on the variables of the rate of economic growth, the rate of poverty and the rate of unemployment that affect the human development index in Sumbawa Regency 2012-2021 can be explained as follows:

The constant value of the regression equation model is 15476,279. This means that if the variable rate of unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, Sumbawa Regency's economic growth rate and Sumbawa Regency's poverty rate is zero or there is no change in the unemployment rate, economic growth rate and poverty rate in Sumbawa Regency, it will result in the human development index in Sumbawa Regency. will not change or remain at 15.47%.

Then partially (t test) regarding unemployment states that the independent variable has a significant influence on the human development index in Sumbawa Regency, because the probability value obtained is smaller than (0.004 < 0.05). The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Moh. Faizin [13] which states that unemployment has a significant influence on the development index in the Regency/City of East Java Province.

The regression coefficient value of the poverty rate in Sumbawa Regency is -1,543. This shows that there is a significant negative effect between the poverty rate in the Sumbawa Regency area and the rate of the human development index level in the Sumbawa Regency, which means that if the poverty rate in the Sumbawa Regency area increases by 1% while the other independent variables remain or are constant, then the index rate rate increases by 1%. human development will decrease -1,543%. This can also be seen from the significance value which shows that the probability value obtained is smaller than (0.000 < 0.05). The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Theogive Maral Sapaat et al [24] which states that the variable number of poor people as an indicator of poverty has a significant negative effect on increasing the human development index in North Sulawesi Province. Likewise with the results of research conducted by Muliza et al. [14], and Umiyati et al. [26] which shows that poverty has a significant and negative effect on the human development index.

The regression coefficient value of the economic growth rate in Sumbawa Regency is -.531. This shows that there is a non-significant negative effect between the rate of economic growth and the human development index in Sumbawa Regency, which means that if the Sumbawa Regency's economic growth rate increases by 1% while other independent variables remain or are constant, then the human development index decreases by -. 531%. This can also be seen from the significance value which shows that the probability value obtained is greater than (0.668 < 0.05). The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted [12] which states that the economic growth variable has no effect on the human development index in the Province of Yogyakarta.

From the results of the explanation above, it shows that the independent variable, namely the poverty rate, has the highest value on the influence of the rate of the human development index level in Sumbawa Regency for the 2012-2021 period. This is due to several things including the economy in Sumbawa Regency which is still dominated by the agricultural sector, namely crop farming, food, livestock, fisheries and forestry. Then the average income of the population in the sector is still less than meeting the basic needs of life. In addition, there are still development disparities between several regions in the West Nusa Tenggara Province, so that it affects the human development index in Sumbawa Regency.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion above that have been discussed previously, the conclusions obtained from this study are: the unemployment rate in Sumbawa Regency, the economic growth rate in Sumbawa Regency and the poverty rate in Sumbawa Regency simultaneously have a significant effect on the rate of the human development index level in the Regency of Sumbawa. Sumbawa in 2012 - 2021. This can be seen in the F test where the significance value is 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Then the independent variable which has the highest level of significance on the human development index in Sumbawa Regency is the poverty rate ($0.000 < 0.05$). Then the second independent variable is the unemployment rate ($0.004 < 0.005$). As for the independent variable, the level of economic growth does not have a significant effect, this is because the economy in Sumbawa Regency is still dominated by the agricultural sector, namely food crop agriculture, animal husbandry, fisheries and forestry. Then the average income of the population in the sector is still less than meeting the basic needs of life. In addition, there are still development gaps between several regions in the province of West Nusa Tenggara, thus affecting the human development index in Sumbawa Regency.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Amalia, R. Y., Fauziah, S., & Wahyuningsih, I. The influence of Islamic finance on economic growth and the human development index in Indonesia, *Al-Muzara'ah*, 7(1), 2019,33–46.
- [2]. Ariza, A. The effect of economic growth and capital expenditure on the human development index in an Islamic perspective, *Al-Maslahah Jurnal Ilmu Syariah*, 12(1), 2016, 1–21.
- [3]. Arizal, M., & Marwan, M. The effect of regional gross domestic product and human development index on the open unemployment rate in West Sumatra Province, *Jurnal Ecogen*, 2(3), 2019, 4-20.
- [4]. Arsyad, L, *Economic development* (Yogyakarta:UPP STIM YKPN, 2006).
- [5]. Baeti, N. Unemployment, economic growth, and government spending on human development in districts/cities in Central Java Province in 2007 – 2011, *Economics Development Analysis Journal*, 2(3), 2013, 85-98.
- [6]. Ghozali, Imam, *Multivariate Analysis Application with SPSS 20 . Program* (Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro, 2013).
- [7]. Hamzah, M. Z., Risqiani, R., & Sofilda, E. Human development quality and its problems in Indonesia, *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 5(7), 2012, 29–36.
- [8]. Hatta, R., & Khoirudin, R. Poverty in NTT Province: A two-panel approach, *Jurnal Samudra Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 11(2), 2020, 138–150.
- [9]. Heka, A. J. L. Government spending on health and education on the human development index in North Sulawesi Province, *EFISIENSI*, 17(1), 2017, 206-217.
- [10]. Kahang, M., Saleh, M., & Suharto, R. B. The effect of government spending on education and health on the human development index in East Kutai Regency, *Forum Ekonomi*, 18(2), 2016, 130–140.
- [11]. Marta, J., Fauzi, A., Juanda, B., & Rustiadi, E. The effect of government spending on education and health on the human development index in East Kutai Regency.
- [12]. Meydiasari, D. A., & Soejoto, A. Analysis of the effect of income distribution, unemployment rate, and government spending on the education sector on the human development index in Indonesia, *JPEKA: Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi, Manajemen dan Keuangan*, 1(2), 2017, 116– 126.
- [13]. Moh. Faizin. Influence of Minimum Wage, Poverty and Unemployment on Human Development Index in Regency/City of East Java Province, *Jurnal Samudra Ekonomi & Bisnis*. 12 (2), 2021, 214 -227.
- [14]. Muliza, M., Zulham, T., & Seftarita, C. Analysis of the effect of education spending, health spending, poverty rate and GRDP on the human development index in Aceh Province, *Jurnal Perspektif Ekonomi Darussalam*, 3(1), 2017, 51–69.
- [15]. Nasution, L. N. Kajian Poverty rate in Batu Bara Regency, North Sumatra Province after the division., *Ekonomikawan, Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi dan Studi Pembangunan*, 19(1), 2019, 13-20.
- [16]. Ningrum, S. S. Analysis of the effect of the open unemployment rate, human development index, and minimum wage on the number of poor people in Indonesia in 2011-2015, *Jurnal Ekonomi Pembangunan*, 15(2), 2017, 184–192.
- [17]. Ningrum, J. W., Khairunnisa, A. H., & Huda, N. The influence of poverty, unemployment rate, economic growth and government spending on the human development index in Indonesia in 2014-2018 from an Islamic perspective, *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Islam (JIEI)*, 6(2),2020, 212–222.
- [18]. Nisa, K., Wulandari, A., & Rahayu, R. L. The effect of income inequality on poverty in the Province of the Bangka Belitung Islands in 2009-2018, *SOROT*, 15(1), 2020, 55– 63.
- [19]. Nugraha, D. P. Poverty in Bengkulu City, what causes it?, *Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi dan Pembangunan (JIEP)*, 20(1), 2020, 31–37.

- [20]. Palenewen, T. O. M., Walewangko, E. N., & Sumual, J. I. The effect of government spending on the education and health sectors on the human development index and its impact on poverty in North Sulawesi, *Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi*, 18(4), 2018, 52-61.
- [21]. Sartika, C., Balaka, M. Y., & Rumbia, W. A.). Study of factors causing poverty in Lohia Village, Lohia District, Muna Regency, *Jurnal Ekonomi (JE)*, 1(1), 2016, 106-118.
- [22]. Syofya, H. Effect of poverty rate and economic growth on Indonesia's human development index, *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 15(2), 2018, 177–185.
- [23]. Sukirno, S. *Macroeconomics introductory theory* (PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2004)
- [24]. Theogive Maral Sapaat et al. Analysis of Factors Affecting Human Development Index In North Sulawesi Province 2005 - 2019, *Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi*. 20 (03), 2020 , 45 -56.
- [25]. Todaro, P. M., & Stephen. C. S. *Economic development* (Jakarta: Publisher Erlangga, 2006).
- [26]. Umiyati, E., Amril, A., & Zulfanetti, Z. The effect of capital expenditures, economic growth and the number of poor people on the human development index in districts/cities of Jambi Province, *Jurnal Sains Sosio Humaniora*, 1(1),2017, 29–37.